

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures in Iraq –

Country Dossier (WP3)

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
The GAPs Project	2
Acknowledgements	3
Funding acknowledgement.....	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Methodology.....	5
3. Context.....	6
3.1 A brief historical review of migration in Iraq	6
3.2 A historical view of the political, economic and social conditions of the infrastructure for return migration in Iraq	7
3.3 Trends and Figures of Return Migration	8
4. Return Migration Infrastructure	9
4.1 Forced Return.....	10
4.2 Assisted return:	11
5. Case Study of Iraq.....	13
5.1 Actors Involved in RMI and their Relations, Implementation, Materials & Technology Provided	13
5.2 National Referral Mechanism (NRM):.....	16
5.2.1 The most important achievements of the NRM:	17
5.2.2 Objectives of the NRM:.....	17
5.2.3 A hypothetical example of a case of the forced return of a returnee from an EU country.....	18
6. Conclusions	20
7. Recommendations:.....	21
8. Sources:	22

List of abbreviations

CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
ETTC	European Technology and Training Centre
EU	European Union
GCM	Global Compact for Migration
GIZ	German International Cooperation Society
HHRO	Hammurabi Human Rights Organization
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IOM	International Organization for Migration
INSS	Iraqi National Security Service
INIS	Iraqi National Intelligence Service
ISIS	Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant
JCC	Joint Crisis Coordination Centre
KRI	Kurdistan Region of Iraq
MOEN	Ministry of Environment
MOFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MOH	Ministry of Health
MOI	Ministry of Interior
MOJ	Ministry of Justice
MOP	Ministry of Planning
MOLSA	Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs
MOMD	Ministry of Migration and Displacement
MOT	Ministry of Trade
MOYS	Ministry of Youth and Sports
NRM	National Referral Mechanism
WEO	Women Empowerment Organization
UMIS	United Iraqi Medical Society for Relief and Development
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Executive Summary

This report provides a snapshot of the nature of the return migration infrastructure in Iraq, represented by the services provided to returning migrants, whether they returned through forced, assisted or voluntary means. The report focuses on Iraqi returnees from EU countries and it starts with a historical overview of the major waves of migration that Iraq has witnessed over the past decades, as well as their motives, time stages, trends, and available numbers over time. The context briefly addresses the social, economic, and political conditions, as well as their repercussions and effects on developing the infrastructure for return migration in Iraq.

The report provides a map of the infrastructure of return migration, explaining the main actors, their roles, and the tasks assigned to each of them in a brief and simplified manner. It also reveals the performance of state agencies, international institutions, the role of humanitarian organizations, the nature of coordination between them, the actors and their various procedures, materials and technologies used, the nature of cooperation and coordination as well as implementation gaps.

The report shows that Baghdad International Airport serves as the exclusive point where deportees from abroad are received, explaining all the steps taken to provide facilities and services before, during and after they arrive at the airport.

The report also highlights Iraq's National Referral Mechanism (NRM)¹, an executive program providing services to returnees, whether forced, assisted or deported. This program is a model for the existing infrastructure framework in Iraq. NRM is the foundational system governing return migration, as it facilitates communication between key stakeholders and coordinates services for returnees. It serves as a model for effective migration governance in Iraq.

In conclusion, the report identifies many obstacles and challenges, presenting several conclusions and recommendations for improving the reality of the infrastructure for return migration in Iraq.

¹ The National Referral Mechanism is a program that has been implemented under the direct supervision and approval of the Iraqi Prime Minister's Office and under the direct guidance and supervision of the Migration and Displacement Ministry, providing electronic services to returnees from the EU who entered this system, to reduce or eliminate bureaucracy in work. This program is an electronic system that provides direct communication between the MOMD and other relevant institutions, such as the MOH, MOI, Ministry of Education, and many other relevant departments that work within it, in addition to eight international organizations and agencies affiliated with the UN and foreign organizations.

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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HHRO Team Main Investigator

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1. Introduction

This country dossier of Iraq is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPs project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is put in practice, through the concept of “Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)”, by focusing on the so-called “crucial meso-level” (Faist 2010). Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (Xiang and Lindquist 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (“doings”), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape – i.e. facilitate or undermine and contest – the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground through a range of practices (Koinova et al. 2021). Moreover, WP3 investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMIs, namely the assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks, by going beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness VS forced returns (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024). WP3 research was implemented in both EU and non-EU countries, particularly in Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden, and Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. EU partner countries focus on RMIs returning people from the EU to either EU – in the case of Dublin – or non-EU and non-EU partners focus on RMIs receiving returnees from the EU.

To study the infrastructures of return migration in Iraq, forced deportation was selected as a case study, and the focus was on Baghdad International Airport as the exclusive reception point designated by Iraqi authorities to receive returnees, whether it is a forced or assisted return. A federal reception committee was formed from stakeholders and by a federal government decision, pursuant to an official letter containing Prime Minister's Office approval No. 2321169/3050, which was issued on 7/25/2023. According to this, the authorities concerned with receiving the deportees were identified and Baghdad International Airport was considered the exclusive place to receive them as a one stop shop for integration, in light of Iraq's international obligations as a supporter of the Global Compact for Migration (GCM) to enhance cooperation on readmission and integration besides improving technical capacities in managing return migration.

Central to this governance framework is Iraq's National Referral Mechanism (NRM), which plays a pivotal role in structuring and coordinating the various components of return migration. The NRM has established a systematic approach to managing the return of migrants as well as safeguarding the rights of returned migrants to receive the essential services needed for their reintegration. Additionally, NRM has strengthened cooperation among government agencies, international organizations, and civil society, and exemplifies a comprehensive strategy aimed at improving the overall infrastructure for migration governance in Iraq, aligned with the objectives outlined in the GCM. It is an executive program in which a group of ministries, state institutions and the Representative Office of the Kurdistan Region of Iraq participate, to refer the deportee to the appropriate party concerned to receive necessary services in terms of health, education, legal, and other services. Therefore, this program was also focused on in this report. Through this program, the governance level of return migration in Iraq, the nature of its effectiveness, the level of coordination between the main actors and the effectiveness of their roles in the return migration issue, as well as the services provided, are determined.

2. Methodology

The WP3 research lasted from June 2023 to June 2024 and included two main tasks. First, creating an overview of RMIs in each partner country by producing flow maps through desk research, which included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc., on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around: i) the actors involved, ii) their actions, and, iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removal, and pushbacks) as a case study. The research started from a specific “entry point” on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of 7 interviews in each country with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, which may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees were provided with an Information Letter and signed the Consent Form of participation in the research. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions, on a voluntary basis.

In addition to what was relied upon in the office work on data, literature, official books, studies and previous reports from Iraqi and international institutions and organizations, specific information was collected based on two approaches to the case study.

Firstly: The report relies on what benefited from the participation of Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (HHRO) researchers in the training workshops referred to below, which were organized by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in cooperation with the Migration and Displacement Ministry (MOMD). The first workshop was titled “The GCM and the Global Migration Law”. This was carried out in Sulaymaniyah for 7 days with the participation of stakeholders from government agencies. The second training workshop titled “Migration terminology and proposed plans to reintegrate returnees (voluntary, forced and supported)”, was held in Erbil for 7 days. The third workshop titled “A comprehensive development program for return and reintegration principles and monitoring mechanisms” was held in Baghdad for 4 days, and the fourth training workshop titled “Strengthening support services for returnees in the long term” was held in Sulaymaniyah for 7 days. The fifth training workshop was entitled “Migration Governance Program”. This was implemented in Baghdad for 5 days, and was supported and funded by the Dutch government within the COMPASS program, which is a program for Iraq in coordination with the Federal Government and the Kurdistan Region and is implemented through the IOM. This focuses on several axes, most importantly supporting and assisting the government in various migration issues by providing technical support, capacity building and assisting the MOMD, the Ministry of Interior (MOI) and the Joint Coordination Crisis Centre (JCC) in Erbil, in the process of reintegration of returnees from abroad.

Secondly: The researchers benefited from interviews with (30) Iraqi returnees from European Union countries, where the interviews were conducted within the tasks of the eighth work package of the GAPs project, in addition to (9) individual meetings with stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental bodies, (7) of which were recorded and were referred in the context by codes, and two of them preferred to be oral and not written down or recorded for personal reasons. The interviews included the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MOFA), MOI, Ministry of Justice (MOJ), Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs (MOLSA), and

Ministry of Youth (MOYS). The researchers also benefited from meetings with international and local organizations such as the IOM and the European Technology and Training Centre (ETTC), and the outcomes of the roundtable conducted by HHRO in April 2024, in which representatives of the General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers, Ministry of Health (MOH), MOJ, Ministry of Planning (MOP), MOLSA, Ministry of Environment (MOEN), and international and local organizations such as IOM, International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) and ETTC participated. The interviews with some stakeholders faced difficulties and challenges due to the fact that they hold senior positions in governmental institutions and there are restrictions on giving information to civil society organizations due to government directives. Moreover, a number of returnees from migration were reluctant to participate in the research due to social and security reasons.

3. Context

3.1 A brief historical review of migration in Iraq

The history of Iraq since its establishment as a state in 1921 has witnessed waves of migration and displacement due to its political, security and economic instability. Their causes range from political, religious, national, economic, legal and psychological situations to wars and conflicts. They may also include other additional reasons. The migration of Iraqis was more collective than individual and was characterized by being closer to displacement or deportation, whether forced or voluntary or “a combination of the two”. Internal and external factors played a vital role in the level of their continuation and occurrence.

Some of the migration was due to internal historical factors that had been fueled from time to time, and some of it was due to political conflicts that sometimes took on a violent character, but in the last two decades, these bore a sectarian and religious dimension.

The waves of migration in Iraq can be summarized into six waves within time periods that witnessed large and collective migrations, as follows:

- The first wave of migration: After what was called the “July 14, 1958 Revolution”, and the change of the monarchy to a republic, and the killing of Iraq’s King and some of his entourage. As a result, followers and supporters of the monarchy left for political and security reasons, and this period extended to include those who left Iraq after the 1963 coup (this wave was limited in number).

- The second wave of migration: This occurred in the late seventies and included tens of thousands of Iraqis due to repressive campaigns that increased during that period by the then-ruling Baath Party against opponents due to political differences, and most of the immigrants were leftists and Islamists (Shiban A., 2017).

- The third wave: This was during the period of the Iran-Iraq war and the First Gulf War against Iraq in 1991, and included those fleeing the crossfire of war, as well as the forced displacement of tens of thousands of Iraqis by the ruling regime due to being considered Iranian subjects. That period was also characterized by a wave of migration of large numbers of minorities, especially Christians and Fayli Kurds (Arab reform net, 2021).

- The fourth wave: This wave occurred following the invasion of Kuwait (1990-2003) and the imposition of an economic embargo against Iraq, which continued for 13 years. This had a negative impact on the economic reality and the deterioration of Iraqis’ living conditions,

contributing significantly to the rise in the level of emigration, as hundreds of thousands of Iraqis were forced to leave the country and seek asylum in Europe, America, Australia and elsewhere. The number of Iraqis living abroad in 2003 was estimated at five million (Migration Policy Institute, 2008).

- The fifth wave, which was the largest mass-migration to occur in a short period, began after the American occupation of Iraq in 2003 and included hundreds of thousands of Iraqis from the country's different regions and its social, religious and ethnic components, including thousands of scientists, intellectuals, academics, doctors, engineers and military personnel. Its pace increased during the years 2006-2008 when targeting and "killing based on identity" intensified, leading to the emigration of politicians and Baathists who were targeted by the "de-Baathification" law (Shiban A., 2017).

- The sixth wave: This was a migration that began with internal displacement that mostly targeted minorities, especially Christians in Basra, Baghdad, Kirkuk and Mosul, after 2003. The largest part of them settled in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI), and from there they headed outside of Iraq. However, this wave intensified to uproot the presence of Christians and Yazidis from their original areas when the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIS) occupied Nineveh Governorate in the summer of 2014, when more than half of the number of Iraqi Christians emigrated. Unofficial statistics indicate that their current number in Iraq does not exceed 300,000 Iraqi Christians out of a total of one and a half million in 2003 (Al-Hurra, 2020). The largest part migrated due to the violence that swept the country and their targeting by terrorist groups, the latest of which was the ISIS invasion of their areas in Mosul and the Nineveh Plain, and more than 100,000 Iraqi Yazidis have migrated abroad since 2014 (Al-Jazeera TV, 2021).

3.2 A historical view of the political, economic and social conditions of the infrastructure for return migration in Iraq

Migration infrastructure is one of the main factors that effectively influences return migration. The more there is governance and development in the level of infrastructure for return migration, the higher the level of return migration and the less Iraqis migrate abroad, thus enhancing the opportunities for the development of the Iraqi economy and sustainable development programs in Iraq.

The infrastructure for migration and return include laws, plans, strategies, actors, materials, technologies, public services such as transportation, health and education and the relationship between all the above.

Therefore, Iraq was greatly affected by decades of political crises, wars, armed conflicts and violence that prevailed in the country for more than four decades. These led to the deterioration of infrastructure, and contributed to the influx of millions of Iraqis outside the country and the country losing enormous human resources of intellectuals, scientists, academics, engineers, doctors, and professionals of various other competencies.

On this basis, Iraq began to establish the MOMD after 2003 to organize the conditions of the estimated 5 million Iraqis who had emigrated or were displaced since the 1970s or before and until 2003 (Migration Policy Institute, 2008). The ministry played a notable role in providing services and developing the conditions of return, whether for those internally displaced or returning from abroad. It thus contributed to issuing legislation to encourage

skilled Iraqi migrants to return to the country.² This provided rights for the return of scientific, professional and academic competencies by granting them the privileges specified in government decision No. 441, dated 14/12/2008, and encouraging them to return. This was especially for those who left Iraq after the intensification of sectarian fighting and acts of killing based on identity that continued between 2006 and 2008, resulting in an increase of emigration and displacement rates, and even undermining the momentum of return that Iraqis abroad were yearning for after the end of the dictatorial regime in 2003.

After the relative stability that followed, Iraq returned to drawing a roadmap and developing a strategy to limit illegal immigration, ratifying a set of international treaties on human rights and joining the GCM in 2018. Moreover, the issue of the return of displaced persons and refugees was placed as one of the axes in the government program of current Prime Minister, Mohammed Shia al-Sudani. In this context, the NRM emerged as a vital component in improving migration governance within return migration by providing a structured framework that facilitates smoother return processes and ensures that returnees receive necessary support and services upon their arrival.

However, there are many challenges that have to be met and solved in order to develop the return migration infrastructure (RMI) in Iraq, including the absence of funds and other financial resources for this purpose which are lacking due to the decline in the global market's oil prices, since this is the main source of funding for the state's general budget. Additionally, Iraq's reconstruction costs after the US occupation and the destruction of strategic infrastructure facilities absorbed a significant portion of financial resources for reconstruction that would have otherwise been directed, whether directly or indirectly, to the economy. This included the depreciation of the Iraqi dinar against the US dollar and the delay in the approval of the state's general budget, which posed additional challenges that adversely impacted the capacity of those charged with migration and return to address and develop infrastructure problems. In addition, political crises, sectarian conflicts, and previous wars had adverse effects on the security situation's instability, and the preoccupation of government institutions with maintaining efforts in the fight against internal conflicts and counter terrorism weakened the interest in providing services to society such as housing, employment and tackling unemployment. The return migration infrastructure also faced legal issues and the administrative bureaucracy slows down the return migration process. This makes rebuilding and enhancing the infrastructure a challenging process not only in terms of finance, economy, politics and society, but also demonstrates challenges in rebuilding confidence and improving stability in society.

3.3 Trends and Figures of Return Migration

After 2003 and the fall of the dictatorial regime in Iraq, there was a clear return of Iraqis to the homeland, especially Iraqi competencies and experienced scientific cadres of doctors and engineers, and their number reached hundreds of thousands (Zayer H., 2018), especially after the issuance of Resolution No. 441 by the Iraqi Council of Ministers, dated 14/12/2008, which included them in many privileges. This resolution granted broad rights to holders of higher degrees (masters and doctorates), holders of higher diplomas, doctors, specialists, and

² Iraq Council of Ministers Resolution No. 441 of the year 2008.

engineers with higher degrees who emigrated outside Iraq due to the former regime's arbitrary actions or were forced to leave Iraq until 1/1/2008, provided that their period of residence abroad was not less than one year. It is worth noting that there are no accurate figures, data and statistics on the number of Iraqis who have returned during the past two decades, and there is no census or mechanism to monitor the cases of return and their nature (Al-Mashhad TV, 2024).

However, this return gradually decreased due to acts of violence and sectarian fighting over identity between 2006 and 2008, and many of those who returned to Iraq emigrated again in search of safety.

The return of unskilled workers faced many challenges due to the lack of clear laws for their reception and integration, along with the absence of advanced and appropriate infrastructure.

4. Return Migration Infrastructure

4.1 Forced Return

After the spread of violence in Iraq after 2003, and the increase in the activity of terrorist groups such as Al-Qaeda and ISIS, Iraq adopted a policy of not accepting the forced return of Iraqi refugees scattered in diaspora countries. This was out of fear for their lives and the state's inability to protect them, as well as the lack of sufficient infrastructure to verify the returnees' identities and their criminal records in diaspora countries. Negotiations between the Iraqi Government and EU thus continued in this direction to accept forced return, until it resulted in the signing of an Association Agreement with the EU and Article 105 of it was clear regarding the acceptance of forced returns of Iraqis, including those sentenced or convicted in EU countries as well. This came into effect in May 2023, after Iraq had signed a Declaration of Goodwill with five EU countries (Germany, the Netherlands, Austria, Finland, and Sweden) regarding refoulement (Interview with: 3MOHM- Meso-M).

Accordingly, Figure 1 illustrates the outlines of refoulement and its infrastructure starts from the returnee's point of departure from the host country. This includes the main actors, their work, main tasks and the materials and technologies they use in the service of return migration.

As the returnee's journey begins, the MOFA, through its embassies, coordinates and cooperates with the department of immigration in the host countries, confirms the returnee's identity and that he/she is an Iraqi citizen, his/her record and biography, and the reasons for his/her return. The Iraqi MOI also verifies the individual's data within Iraq and this process is also coordinated with. Embassies issue travel documents for one time use only to those who do not have a passport and give information and directions concerning Iraq's programs for returnees. The MOFA also coordinates with the Iraqi Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) to give information on flights, times and the airlines by which the returnees will leave the country as well as inform the airport of the returnees' arrival times. The MOFA applies several techniques in this regard, such as diplomatic mail, electronic correspondence, travel documents (passports), as well as publications and leaflets informing people of Iraq's policies and programs for returnees from the diaspora.

Figure 1 shows, in detail, the tasks of each ministry, the nature of its work and the services it performs for the returnee's benefit, as well as what techniques and materials it uses to carry out its tasks. The table additionally includes the tasks and work of the MOI, its role, techniques and materials used for implementation, and also the MOLSA, MOMD, MOH, MOJ, and the Ministry of Trade (MOT). These ministries additionally have representatives in the committee for receiving returnees based at Baghdad International Airport and led by the MOMD. Representatives of government bodies other than ministries in this committee include security agencies such as the Iraqi National Intelligence Service (INIS) and the Iraqi National Security Service (INSS), as well as the Joint Crisis Coordination Center (JCC) in the KRI.

These ministries and institutions work in coordination and cooperation within the NRM, which was established in 2020 by order of the Iraqi Prime Minister as part of the national strategy to curb illegal immigration.

The NRM is headed by the MOMD, which refers the returnee to the relevant authorities on the basis of his/her needs. If their needs are health-related, such as requiring a check-up or vaccination, they are then referred to the MOH. If they have an education need for themselves or their children, they are referred to the Education Ministry. If they lack or have lost their identity documents, they are referred to the MOI. Because we considered this program as a case study, and to avoid repetition, we explained in detail the points in Figure 1 in terms of the work and services provided by each ministry or institution, as well as the materials and technologies they use after the returnee returns and is registered in the program.

4.2 Assisted return:

Figure 2 shows that the parties involved in the return assistance program are some Iraqi ministries, as well as international and local organizations that cooperate with each other. The most important of these are the MOMD, MOI, INSS, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), IOM, German International Cooperation Society (GIZ), United Iraqi Medical Society for Relief and Development (UMIS), ETTC, Women Empowerment Organization (WEO), ICMPD, and HHRO.

There is also cooperation between the MOMD and international institutions in accordance with memoranda and cooperative protocols (such as the IOM and the International Center for Child Policy Development) to provide specific services to returnees. There is also coordination between the IOM, UNHCR and MOMD in developing return policies in Iraq, especially voluntary and assisted return, as well as with other local organizations, including HHRO, which is considered a partner of MOMD.

Figure 2 also shows the types of services that are provided by each agency or organization and the technologies that are used in the provision of these services. For instance, cash is provided by the host countries, which purchase air tickets for the returnees and pay for the services of local organizations such as the ETTC and the ICMPD. These in turn furnish and pay for returnees' accommodation for the initial period of time and refer them to medical and health facilities. They provide awareness information through brochures, conduct training for returnees, pay school fees for children and provide returnees with a welcome pack that includes basic things like toothpaste, water and a SIM card. For instance, if we consider the HHRO, it develops studies, research and reports on returnees and refugees, observes and reports on their situation and supports them to get work by providing money to start small businesses for returnees and training programs to enhance their capacity and improve their standard of living.

5. Case Study of Iraq

As Iraq is a point of source, transit and destination for migrants, the diversity of migration patterns in the country requires the Iraqi government to consider return and readmission management from multiple perspectives. Iraq not only receives voluntary and forced return requests but also needs to consider rights-based controls from the host country's perspective. For this case study, the focus will be on forced return and the NRM.

The Iraqi Government has a National Migration Management Strategy which was endorsed in 2020 and is used to guide the implementation of the GCM (Mulla W., 2024).

The Iraqi Government thus recognizes that a comprehensive approach to migration management must include a safe, orderly, and rights-based framework for return and readmission in line with the GCM.

5.1 Actors Involved in RMI and their Relations, Implementation, Materials & Technology Provided

As regards the particular procedure (the “doings”) of the Return Migration Infrastructure, the return and readmission is carried out in two stages, each with its own steps, actors, materials and technologies, different from the other, to ensure the process of deportation, acceptance and reintegration with the least possible challenges (Interview with: 3MOHM-Meso-M). To study the case of Iraq, the focus was on forced return, with details provided about the NRM followed in Iraq. The location of Baghdad International Airport was chosen as a central and exclusive location to receive deportees, and centrally register them in the NRM's database.³

A. The first stage begins before the deportee leaves and consists of several steps implemented by the host country, which will be discussed in detail as shown in Figure No. 3.

Figure 3

(HHRO, 2024)

Step one of the first stage: The deportee is notified from the host country to his country of origin (Iraq) in this step of the deportation decision by the Migration Agency

³ HHRO round table with Stakeholder Expert Persons (SEP) discussions.

after being summoned to the headquarters of the host country's Immigration Agency and being informed by means of a written letter sent to the person concerned stating the reasons for the deportation decision, with the departure times specified. He must arrange the context of his return in a semi-voluntary manner. If he exceeds the times granted to him, he is detained in detention centers to arrange his deportation under control. Here, the infrastructure and logistical arrangements must be secured for the period of the deportee's stay in the host country's detention centers.⁴

Step Two: Communication takes place between the host country's migration agency and the Iraqi embassy or consulate during the detention period to verify the deportee's identity and affiliation to the country of origin from the host country's Interior Ministry. The Iraqi embassy/consulate studies the deportee's case, verifies their identity, and prepares to issue a laissez-passer after securing communication with the Iraqi authorities (MOFA, MOI, INIS, INSS, or MOMD) to inform the MOFA of the diplomatic work to secure the return. As for the MOI, through the operations center affiliated with the ministry, the identity of the returnee is verified as being Iraqi. As for the MOMD, it arranges to prepare the infrastructure and logistics to receive the returnees after providing transportation, a ticket and a meal from the host country (Interview with: 3MOHM-Meso-M).

Step Three: Once the relevant authorities verify that the returnee's identification documents are from the country of origin (Iraq), the Iraqi embassy/consulate issues a temporary passport after verifying the returnee's identity and the host country's immigration agencies are notified to coordinate the return (2MFA-Meso-M).

Step Four: The returnee is transferred to the host country's airport for departure after covering the return expenses following coordination between the Iraqi authorities and the host country's immigration agency. The returnee is accompanied by security personnel from the host country to avoid any problems that may occur during the trip.⁵

Step Five: The deportee arrives at the airport of the country of origin (Iraq), where he is received by the relevant authorities to provide him the required services. The Iraqi federal government has designated Baghdad Airport, and not any other, as the airport where returnees will be accepted, to be able to receive them according to the standards set by Iraq (Interview with: 3MOHM-Meso-M). Baghdad Airport, in this way, forms a crucial part of the Return Migration Infrastructure materiality, as it is the place where reception is centralized to ensure documentation and database maintenance, provide immediate services, and direct returnees to the NRM.

⁴ HHRO round table with Stakeholder Expert Persons (SEP) discussions.

⁵ HHRO round table with Stakeholder Expert Persons (SEP) discussions.

B. The Second Stage: This begins when the deportee arrives at the country of origin's airport (Baghdad Airport) and will be discussed in detail as shown in Figure No. 4.

Figure 4

(HHRO, 2024)

Step one of the second stage: Returnees are directed to the reception committee when the deportees' plane lands at Baghdad Airport after notifying the CAA.⁶ In this step, a security check is conducted to determine the returnees' status regarding their criminal records.

Step Two: The returnees' information is entered into the initial registration mechanism in the NRM's database through a paper form prepared for this purpose that includes full name, return destination, passport number, number of family members, type of return, date of departure and arrival, permanent address with the nearest reference point in Iraq, initial security information check, and returnees are given a mobile SIM card to facilitate communication with them.

Step Three: This step implements the NRM by registering the case management at the MOMD, where the reintegration of cases is evaluated, advice is provided to find solutions to the problems facing the returnee, and planning is done to complete transactions in government institutions.

Step Four: This is complementary to the previous step, through follow-up from the National Referral Office with stakeholder departments after assigning an identification code for each returnee to facilitate the provision of services from stakeholders.

Step Five: In this step, support is provided to returnees in coordination with stakeholders by securing financial loans for small and medium enterprises, with the returnee being involved in rehabilitation programs for work in the labor market besides securing study seats for returning students and enrolling them in the path of higher education and teaching.

⁶ Stakeholders in the Reception Committee are Representatives from the MOFA, MOI, MOMD, INIS, INSS, CAA, MOLSA, MOH and the JCC.

Residential lands have also been prepared for distribution to returnees and other services through a national plan for economic, social and psychological reintegration.⁷

Iraq has taken serious steps towards strengthening return and readmission management since the launch of the National Migration Management Strategy. As a member of the Champion countries initiative of GCM, Iraq has shown significant progress in fulfilling its commitments by expanding the NRM (IOM, 2022), enhancing cooperation on readmission and improving technical capacities on returns.

However, there are still challenges to the infrastructure of return, readmission and reintegration management, including the small number of reception centers, poor coordination in the exchange of information between host countries and Iraq on sensitive data related to irregular migration, for example, asylum applications, the health status of deportees, disability, sexual identity and data security. An example of poor coordination is that officials at Baghdad airport may not be aware of the arrival of a group of returnees, as the Iraqi authorities were not notified of those who were returned to Iraq directly from the host country and are sometimes accompanied by police, confusing the CAA's work, in addition to confusion for the workers at the airport reception centers. During interviews conducted, returnees confirmed that the Iraqi authorities were not notified of their arrival, which led to the arrival of a number of returnees to Iraq through Baghdad International Airport without the reception committee meeting them and registering them in the database (1SRK-1WW-Micro-F).

Some issues have additionally emerged, including the weak participation of civil society organizations in the reception committee and the weak funding allocated to it. This makes it awkward to secure the transportation of returnees to their residential areas in the governorates, especially those returning to the KRI, and weak information and data sharing among stakeholders, leading to inaccurate statistics. These issues appear in the first and second steps of the second phase of the return journey.

Recently, Iraq is seeking to adopt an electronic system for managing readmission cases to verify the identities of Iraqis living abroad in line with current procedures and legal frameworks. The MOFA will likely lead this initiative as a link between the MOI and the countries requesting the return of migrants to Iraq, thus facilitating communication during this process. The MOI in Iraq is working on adding this system to link information to the national security systems and the national identity directorates and departments to maintain its database.⁸

5.2 National Referral Mechanism (NRM):

Before we address the case study, we must identify the NRM that emerged from the National Strategy for Migration Management in Iraq. It is an essential part of the government's efforts to promote effective and comprehensive migration governance.

This system aims to provide coordinated and integrated support to migrants, returnees and refugees, and ensure they receive the necessary reintegration services by organizing and coordinating efforts between various stakeholders.

⁷ HHRO round table with Stakeholder Expert Persons (SEP) discussions.

⁸ Interview with a senior officer in the MOI who wanted to be anonymized, June 11, 2024.

5.2.1 The most important achievements of the NRM:

The Achievements include the following:

1. Identifying stakeholders: The system includes identifying governmental and non-governmental bodies concerned with providing services to migrants, returnees, and refugees, including the MOFA, MOI, MOMD, MOLSA, MOJ, INIS, INSS and KRI Representative, as well as national civil society organizations and international organizations (Interview with: 3MOHM-Meso-M).

2. Referral mechanisms: The system defines clear mechanisms for referring cases between different entities to ensure that individuals receive appropriate services quickly and effectively. This includes standardized procedures for assessing individuals' needs and directing them to the relevant competent authorities.

3. Integrated Support: Integrated support is provided, including health, social, legal, and educational services. The system aims to ensure that no one is left without the necessary assistance upon return to Iraq.

4. Case Management: The system includes mechanisms for managing individual cases, where each case is followed up individually to ensure that the person receives the required services, as well as to assess the extent to which these services have improved his social and legal situation.⁹

5. Training and Capacity Building: The system includes training programs for government and NGO employees on how to use the referral system and how to deal with migrants and returnees in ways that respect human rights and meet their needs as well as the work training programs for returnees (Interview with: 3MOHM-Meso-M).

6. Awareness and Communication: The system also focuses on raising awareness of the importance of the migrants' and returnees' rights, as well as how to access the services available to them. This includes media campaigns and awareness programs directed at both returnees and the agencies that provide them with services.

5.2.2 Objectives of the NRM:

• **Ensuring the rights of migrants and returnees:** That every individual gets his/her basic human rights and right to life irrespective of his/her legal, social, ethnic or religious status.

• **Improving coordination between different entities:** Increasing the cooperation of ministries and institutions, as well as national and international civil society organizations, to guarantee an appropriate and coherent response to the needs of returnees

• **Promoting sustainability:** To make sure the services that are provided to migrants and returnees are sustainable and contribute to their integration into society by assessing their work and implementation mechanisms.

The NRM comes in the context of the urgent need to manage the return of displaced persons and migrants humanely and effectively in Iraq, especially after the conflicts that the country has witnessed. The system also contributes to facilitating the reintegration process and

⁹ Live broadcast of the Director General of the Immigration Department in the MOMD, May 27, 2024.

ensures providing protection and basic services to migrants and returnees. However, this program is not perfect and faces challenges in many areas, including the fact that it is a new system and needs a period of time to be practiced, as well as the lack of financial and logistical support and insufficient financial allocations from the state budget for this purpose, which has a significant impact on the program's effectiveness, in addition to the lack of promotion of the work, tasks, materials, technologies and services provided by it. Several interviews conducted by HHRO's research team with tens of returnees showed that returnees have no idea or information about this program, its working mechanisms and the services that it provides to returnees.

5.2.3 A hypothetical example of a case of the forced return of a returnee from an EU country

A person who has been deported from an EU country to Iraq, starting from the moment of arrival at Baghdad Airport receives services and undergoes certain follow-up procedures, which ideally are:

First: The person's arrival at Baghdad Airport after a forced return flight:

A. Reception and initial assessment:

1- Upon arrival at Baghdad International Airport, the reception committee makes an initial assessment of the returnee's case. His/her identity, passport and other travel documents are checked, in addition to examining any arrest warrants or pending legal cases (if any).

2- This assessment may include contacting the EU country authorities to confirm the details of the deportation and the reasons that led to it, in addition to receiving any files or information related to his/her health or legal status that may require immediate follow-up in Iraq.

3- The information and data of the returnee are put into the database of the NRM and he/she is given a mobile chip that can easily be used to contact him/her in the future, and also gives him/her their serial code in the NRM.

4- During this assessment, the immediate needs of the returnee are determined. For example, if he/she is suffering from a medical emergency, medical procedures will be provided by the Baghdad International Airport Medical Clinic.

Second: Referral Procedures: Referring the Returnee to the Competent Authorities:

- **Referral to the MOH:** If the person has health issues of any kind, physical or psychological, he/she is taken directly to the MOH to deliver him/her and give him/her the necessary treatment. It may entail taking him/her to a hospital or clinic for the necessary laboratory investigations.

- **Referral to the MOLSA:** If the person is in need of social or economic support, such as providing shelter or financial assistance, he/she is referred to the MOLSA. The latter, in turn, undertakes to provide the necessary assistance, whether by providing temporary shelter or

engaging him/her in rehabilitation and vocational training programs to help him/her obtain a job opportunity.

- **Referral to the MOI:** If there are legal issues related to the person's status, such as updating documents or resolving pending legal issues, he/she is referred to the MOI to deal with these issues. This may include reissuing the national ID card or passport, or dealing with any other court orders.

Third: Providing services and support:

A. Health support:

1- Urgent health care: The person is transferred to a government hospital or specialized clinic if urgent health care is needed. The necessary treatment is provided and the health condition is followed by specialized medical teams.

2- Psychological support: Psychological support services are provided if the person suffers from psychological trauma or suffers from psychological disorders as a result of deportation. This may include therapy with psychiatrists or counselors who are trained in psychotherapy.

B. Social and economic support:

1- Providing shelter: Temporary shelter is provided through the MOLSA if the person is homeless upon arrival in Iraq. This can be in government shelters or through partnerships with non-governmental organizations.

2- Financial assistance and training programs: The MOLSA can apply for soft loans for small and medium enterprises if the person needs financial support. They can also be involved in vocational training programs aimed at rehabilitating them and integrating them into the local labor market.

C. Legal support:

Resolving legal issues: Legal support is provided through the MOI and the MOJ if there are legal issues that need to be resolved, such as problems related to documents or legal disputes. It is ensured that all necessary documents are updated and that the person receives the required legal assistance.

Fourth: Follow-up and evaluation:

A. Continuous evaluation: The person's case is followed up and periodically monitored by the NRM team to ensure that all the returnee's needs have been adequately met after providing the initial services. This may include field visits, follow-up through phone calls, social media, or communication with the entities that provide electronic services.

B. Improving the socio-economic situation: The person's progress and ability to integrate into the labor market are monitored if he/she is involved in vocational training programs provided by the MOLSA. Additional support is provided if necessary to ensure his/her economic and social stability.

C. A final assessment is conducted after a certain period (every 6 months) to ensure that the person has been successfully integrated into the community. The impact of the support

provided and the extent to which the person has achieved social and economic stability are assessed.

D. Recommendations can be made to improve support and referral mechanisms for returnees in the future based on the final assessment. This may include improving referral protocols or developing new programs that better meet the needs of returnees.

Fifth: Current challenges for the National Referral Mechanism:

A. Challenges in updating documents: The deported person may face difficulties in updating his/her official documents, especially if there are legal issues, or if the documents are lost or damaged, in addition to processing educational documents for returnees and their family members and enrolling them in school.

B. Ensuring legal protection: In some cases, there may be a need to provide additional legal protection for the returnees, for example, when they are faced with financial threats or legal issues in the country from which he/she was deported.

C. Sometimes, there is **no coordination** with the relevant authorities of the country of origin (Iraq) and the forced deportation takes place directly from the host country's airport to Baghdad International Airport, which confuses the authorities at the airport as it requires keeping the returnee at the airport's detention center. Baghdad International Airport has an airport police station, where deportees are detained until their identification papers and affiliation to the country of origin are verified. This has happened on many occasions and Iraqis who returned to Iraq and were interviewed stated that they had arrived at Baghdad Airport after they were deported but found that the Iraqi authorities had no knowledge of this. They were thus not received by the relevant committee due to the weak coordination between the deportee's host country and the Iraqi authorities.

Despite all these challenges the NRM is a vital part of the national strategy for managing migration in Iraq. It is a pioneering experience through which Iraq is trying to guarantee that people who return from abroad get the integrated support they need to return to society in a way that respects their dignity and helps to maintain their social and economic stability.

6. Conclusions

1. The analysis indicates the need to adapt an integrated vision for the development of migration, return and integration infrastructure, in addition to the importance of supporting the return and migration plan adopted by Iraq to encourage migrants to return in an organized and systematic manner, so that stakeholders in Iraq and those active in the return of migrants and refugees can achieve effective and comprehensive governance in this regard and contribute to the development and building of more stable and cohesive societies.

2. Iraq has been plagued by political crises, wars, armed conflicts and violence for more than four decades, making return migration infrastructure an urgent necessity to develop.

3. It is necessary to simplify procedures and laws to improve the infrastructure environment to be more effective.

4. There is weak coordination between international actors and Iraq, as there have been many times in which deportees have arrived without prior notification to Iraqi authorities. This causes confusion in the reception process as a result of poor coordination between the official authorities of the country of deportation and the country of reception.

5. The lack of support centers in the governorates to support deportees because they are from different regions of Iraq, especially those returning to the KRI, causes confusion in maintaining the database at the MOMD's central station.

6. The NRM is a new system with several potentials. The analysis of the migration infrastructure in Iraq has demonstrated the NRM's critical role as the cornerstone of migration governance in Iraq. The NRM manages the complexities of return migration—covering the processes involved in the safe and dignified return of migrants. It also plays a significant role in strengthening a more sustainable and stable environment for returnees.

7. Recommendations:

1. The Iraqi government should enhance collaboration and coordination with the EU countries transparently through protocols of understanding to organize the stages of the return of irregular migrants to Iraq in a way that preserves the dignity of returnees in accordance with human rights principles. It is necessary to announce these protocols, or bilateral or multilateral agreements, with transparency to be a roadmap for work and coordination between all parties.

2. The return migration infrastructure is a vital area where the Iraqi Government should invest its money in order to improve return migration infrastructures such as health, education, transportation and public services, while international support should be used to improve this environment.

3. Working to improve management and strategic planning of infrastructure projects in Iraq for migration such as laws and legislation, as well as developing serious projects for the reception and integration of refugees.

4. To ensure a rapid and immediate response, it is necessary to develop clear and detailed protocols and commit to transparency to coordinate between all stakeholders, in order to facilitate the reception process. Additionally, the stakeholders should exchange information between themselves.

5. Develop comprehensive vocational training programs targeting groups returning from abroad to help them integrate into the local labor market, with the support of the Labor and Migration Resource Center at the MOLSA.

6. Support the NRM in both Iraq and the KRI to provide psychological support programs dedicated to returnees who may suffer from trauma or psychological stress as a result of their experiences of deportation or forced expulsion.

7. The Iraqi government should allocate a special budget to support return, readmission and integration programs for returnees.

8. Emphasize effective coordination between the Iraqi federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government to follow up on returnees in general by exchanging information and standardizing the database.

9. Involving and cooperating with civil society organizations (national and international) in the return migration issue, as well as in providing services to returnees through the NRM. The Iraqi government and EU countries should prioritize strengthening the NRM to enhance its capacity for effective migration governance. This includes investing in technological improvements, training programs for staff in new locations, and increasing funding to ensure that it can meet the growing needs of returnees.

10. Enhancing cooperation between state institutions and civil society organizations related to migration and return.

11. Implementing awareness campaigns to inform returnees and the broader community about the NRM and the services available to them.

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